

Quantitative analysis of ophiomicrodermatoglyphics in shed-off skin: a novel taxonomic approach in snake identification

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Proper snake identification is essential for ecological research, conservation, and snakebite management, especially regarding venomous species. However, Traditional morphological methods pose envenomation risks during live handling, while molecular approaches require specialized equipment and expertise, limiting their practicality and emphasize the need for safer, more accessible alternatives. This study introduces a novel, non-invasive identification method using microdermatoglyphic features from shed-off snake skin. We examined six microdermatoglyphic characters from fifteen representative scales from the head, body and tail region of *Naja kaouthia* and *Naja naja*. Statistical analyses revealed that these features can reliably distinguish the two species and also differentiate between sexes. Among the characters, edge widest part distance (edge_wpd) was the most discriminative, significantly ($p < 0.001$) separating 93.33% of the studied scales, followed by edge_area (86.67%) and number of follicles per 20,000 μm^2 (46.67%). Microdermatoglyphic characters also significantly ($p < 0.001$) differentiated males and females in both *Naja kaouthia* and *Naja naja*, with edge_area being the most effective character distinguishing 60% of scales in *N. kaouthia* and 20% in *N. naja*, followed by number of follicles per 20,000 μm^2 (folli_20_thou), which differentiated 33% of scales in *N. kaouthia* and 13% in *N. naja*. This non-invasive approach to snake identification provides biologists a promising tool for snake taxonomy that will help better study biodiversity.

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